

Digital Literacy: The Outcome of Online Learning Satisfaction

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ABSTRACT

The development of technology has also transformed how students learn. The study examines the digital literacy level of student with their online learning satisfaction. A total of 210 randomly selected undergraduate students of San Isidro College served as the participants of the study. The study implemented a correlational research design and adopted the questionnaire anchored on the digital literacy skills framework and online learning satisfaction questionnaire. The study revealed that the student's digital literacy is on the second level. Overall, they are satisfied with their online learning experience. However, the literacy level and online learning satisfaction has a weak relationship.

Subject Area

Online Learning

Keywords: *Digital Literacy, Online Learning Satisfaction, Online Learning, Educational Technology*

INTRODUCTION

Technology has transformed the way people communicate, engage, and work, but it is not only limited to society. The way students learn has also changed as a result of technological advancement. Digital literacy, also known as virtual learning or e-learning, has the potential to help students for lifelong learning (Shopova, 2014; Loveless, n.d.). The current generation of learners are well versed in using technology, ranging from entertainment to learning. Students use technology to make learning easier and perform task with efficiency (PowerSchool, 2021).

Learning satisfaction comes as the effect of the teaching and learning process where the student participates in the class or discussion (Wu, Hsieh, and Lu, 2014). Communication, student participation in online discussions, flexibility, workload, technological assistance, instructor pedagogical knowledge, and feedback are all aspects that contribute to student satisfaction in online learning (Elshami, et al., 2021). According to Cheok and Wong (2015) students are more assured in their online learning when they are confident in their skill in using technology.

Numerous educational establishments were compelled by COVID-19 to switch from in-person instruction to online instruction. Utilizing readily available technological tools and appropriate learning platforms, allowed the schools to adjust to the sudden transition (Godber and Atkins, 2021). The United States published that 88% of teens have access to and are well versed in online platforms (Johnson, 2021). The Philippines on the other hand stated that 86% of college students aged 18-24 have accessed and are well versed in the online platforms (Statista Research Department, 2021).

Many students are considered to be technological natives and implies that they are well suited to the technological advancements of the digital era (Dingli and Setchell, 2015). The study seeks to learn the relationship between digital literacy and online learning satisfaction of students enrolled during the academic year 2021-2022. Establishing the relationship between digital literacy and online learning satisfaction could help improve the learning experience of the students and further improve the student's digital literacy. Additionally, establishing the student's digital literacy could improve the use of educational technology in the practice of instruction.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The study adopts the design theory of technology-based student-centered learning (Hannafin & Land, 1997) as an initial foundation to explore elements of an online student-centered learning environment. Additionally, the study anchors on the paper of McLean, Oldfield, and Stephen (2020) on the Digital Literacy Skills Framework that helps assess student knowledge on digital literacy. The study involves evaluating the students' digital literacy and measures the students online learning satisfaction during the COVID-19 Pandemic.

Digital literacy is defined as the physical operation of digital devices and software's within the devices (UNESCO, 2018). Digital literacy is the ability to navigate, locate, collaborate, think critically, process information, and address individual safety and well-being using various digital technologies (McLean, Oldfield, and Stephens, 2020). Online learning satisfaction is defined as complex and multidimensional which includes varied factors such as communication, participation of students on online discussions, knowledge and support on technology, the flexibility of the workload of instructors and students, the pedagogical skill of instructors, and the feedback provided to students (Wei and Chou, 2020).

The conceptual framework of the study as shown in Figure 1 illustrates the correlation design. The independent variable is the students' digital literacy and the dependent variable is the online learning satisfaction.

Figure 1

Schematic diagram of the conceptual framework of the study

The digital literacy has four levels that determines the students' proficiency in using technology and online platforms. Online learning satisfaction considered seven (7) factors. The factor on *Background* establishes the students' idea and understanding on online modalities and learning platforms. The factor on *Learning Outcomes* measures students' exposure and experience

to the learning outcomes of the course that they are taking. The factor on *Assessment and Measurement* assesses the students' experience on the quizzes and examinations that they were given during the duration of the course.

The factor on *Learning Resource and Materials* evaluates the students' experience with their learning material and other supplemental resources used in the course. The factor on *Learner Interaction with Instructor* assesses the students' experience with their interaction to their instructors on both classes and online communication. The factor in *Learner Interaction* checks the students' relationship between one another. And, the factor on *Online Technology* evaluates the students' background on online resources and platforms used in classes.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The study examined the student's digital literacy level and online learning satisfaction at San Isidro College during the Academic Year 2021-2022. Specifically, it answered the following:

1. What is the level of digital literacy of the students?
2. What is the online learning satisfaction of the students?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of student's digital literacy and their online learning satisfaction?

RESEARCH DESIGN

The study utilizes a correlation method to establish a relationship between students' level of digital literacy and online learning satisfaction. San Isidro College serves as the research local of the study. San Isidro College (SIC) is the only Catholic institution of higher learning in the City of Malaybalay, and the oldest in the province of Bukidnon. The study was conducted among the 210 college students enrolled for the Academic Year 2021-2022.

The major instrument adopted for the study was the questionnaire developed by Papas Education (2020) anchored on the paper of McLean, Oldfield, and Stephens (2020) on digital literacy. The instrument has twenty (20) questions following the Digital Literacy Skills Framework. The instrument of Aman (2009) was also used on online learning satisfaction with twenty-five (25) question. The digital literacy questionnaire consists of a 4-point scale. The questionnaire self-evaluates the students' level of digital literacy. The questionnaire has a Cronbach alpha of 0.737. The criteria use the range developed by McLean, Oldfield, and Stephens (2020) following:

<u>Scale</u>	<u>Range</u>	<u>Qualitative Interpretation</u>
4	3.26 – 4.00	<i>Digital Literacy Level 3</i>
3	2.51 – 3.25	<i>Digital Literacy Level 2</i>
2	1.76 – 2.50	<i>Digital Literacy Level 1</i>
1	1.00 – 1.75	<i>Digital Literacy Pre-Level 1</i>

The questionnaire developed by Amon (2009) contains seven (7) major factors, namely: *Background* with three (3) statements reflecting the students background on online learning. The second factor is *Learning Outcome* with four (4) statements reflecting the students experience with the learning outcomes provided in their classes. The third factors consist of *Assessment & Measurement* with five (5) statements reflecting the students experience with the quizzes and

exams taken. The fourth factor is on *Learning Resource & Materials* with five (5) statements reflecting the students experience with the class materials.

The fifth factor is on *Learner Interaction* with Instructor with three (3) statements that evaluates the students experience with their interaction to their instructor. The sixth factor is *Learner Interaction* with two (2) statements that evaluates the students' relationships. And the last factor is *Online Technology* which evaluates the students experience with online technology. The online learning satisfaction follow a 5-point Likert scale. It evaluates the students online learning satisfaction. The questionnaire has a Cronbach-alpha of 0.741. The criteria used the following:

<u>Scale</u>	<u>Range</u>	<u>Qualitative Interpretation</u>
5	4.21 – 5.00	<i>Very Satisfied</i>
4	3.41 – 4.20	<i>Satisfied</i>
3	2.61 – 3.40	<i>Neither Satisfied nor Unsatisfied</i>
2	1.81 – 2.60	<i>Unsatisfied</i>
1	1.00 – 1.80	<i>Very Satisfied</i>

The data employed the descriptive statistics, specifically the mean, to determine the digital literacy of the students. ANOVA test to compare the satisfaction of the seven parameters of online satisfaction and Pearson moment correlation r to establish the relationship of digital literacy and online satisfaction.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Digital Literacy Level

Table 1 presents the means score with the qualitative interpretation on the level of digital literacy and presents the level of satisfaction of the students.

Table 1

Level of digital literacy of the students

PARAMETER	MEAN	S.D.	QUALITATIVE INTERPRETATION
Digital Literacy	2.78	0.460	Digital Literacy Level 2

As shown in Table 1, the digital literacy of the student falls under the second level. The results indicate that the students can display understanding as a digital user and that they can use a limited set of strategies to operate digital software and tools while being familiar with the context. Moreover, students are able to complete tasks effectively, but requires support especially on complicated task or unfamiliar contexts (Papas Education, 2020).

Furthermore, learners can connect and collaborate with other individuals while using a wide variety of devices and software. The learners are able to understand and apply a limited set of digital netiquettes and use the internet for activities and connections. In addition, the learners can demonstrate some insight when sharing information on the internet and understand the importance of security and privacy (McLean, Oldfield, and Stephens, 2020; Yong-Young, Yeon-Woo, and Hye-Jin, 2021).

Online Learning Satisfaction

Table 2 presents the comparison of the seven (7) factors of online learning. Additionally, Table 2 shows the mean score with qualitative interpretation on the seven (7) factors of online learning satisfaction and presents the degree of satisfaction of the students.

Table 2*Online learning satisfaction of the students*

PARAMETER	MEAN	Q.I.	<i>f</i>	<i>p</i>
Learning Interaction	3.93 a	Satisfied		
Learning Outcomes	3.85 ab	Satisfied		
Assessment and Measurement	3.82 b	Satisfied		
Learning Resource and Materials	3.82 b	Satisfied	13.471	0.000**
Background	3.78 bc	Satisfied		
Online Course Technology	3.70 bc	Satisfied		
Learner Interaction with Instructors	3.61 c	Satisfied		
OVERALL	3.79	Satisfied		

NOTE: ** – significant at 0.01

As shown in Table 2, the students were satisfied in their overall online learning. Moreover, the learners are effective in all parameters under online learning satisfaction. The *f*-value of the parameters are 13.471 with a *p*-value of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$), indicating that there is a significant difference between the parameters. Additionally, Table 2 illustrates that *Learning Interaction* showed that the learners are most satisfied and *Learner Interaction with Instructors* is the parameter that the students were least satisfied with.

Online instruction has provided an avenue for students to find methods of learning, one method could be to interact with one another. Students who have difficulty would opt to contact their peers in order to ask for clarification or insights (Avila and Genio, 2020; Godber and Atkins, 2021). Student would use their online platforms to create communication channels that would benefit them and create a discussion medium for idea exchange (Dingli and Setchell, 2015). However, communication with instructors is a problem for some students since they are not familiar with some of their instructors or are afraid or anxious when communicating with them (Barrot, Llanares, del Rosario, 2021; Joaquin, Biana, and Dacela, 2020).

Relationship between Digital Literacy and Online Learning Satisfaction

Table 3 presents the extent of association between the digital literacy level and the online learning satisfaction.

Table 3*Relationship between Digital Literacy and Online Learning Satisfaction*

VARIABLE	MEAN	<i>r</i>	EXTENT OF RELATIONSHIP
Digital Literacy	3.79	0.247	Weak Positive Relationship
Online Learning Satisfaction	2.78		

As presented in Table 3, the correlation value is 0.247 which indicates a low correlation between variables and the result also indicates that the relationship is weak. The findings propose that the digital literacy of the learners has a weak relationship with their online learning

satisfaction. The result implies that the students' digital literacy level has only a weak impact to their satisfaction in learning online. The result is supported by Table 2 which shows that the *Online Course Technology* ranked sixth among the seven parameters. This suggests that learners are more attentive to other aspects of online learning and focus on what to learn rather than technical knowledge of their devices.

The results of the study of Yong-Young, Yeon-Woo, and Hye-Jin (2020) and Vermisli, Cevik, and Cevik, (2022) support the positive relationship of digital literacy towards online learning satisfaction. Claiming that a student's level of knowledge on technology has a positive effect in distance learning. Moreover, students who are proficient in technology could do well in doing online task like encoding, manipulating learning platforms, data mining, and communicating with other learners (Atoy, M. Jr, et al., 2020).

SUMMARY

The study discovered the impression of digital literacy towards online learning satisfaction. The study reveals that the digital literacy of the learners is on the second level. The study also reveals that the learners are most satisfied with their learning interaction and least satisfied with their interactions with the instructors. Overall, they are satisfied with the online learning experience. Moreover, the study revealed that the student's digital literacy level has a weak relationship with their online learning satisfaction. The digital literacy of the students has a weak bearing on their online learning satisfaction.

Supplementary studies can be conducted, exploring the factors that affect the student's digital literacy and influences on the levels of digital literacies. Additionally, a study may be conducted to further explore the views on digital literacy and online learning.

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